

WOMEN'S POWER

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Abstract. *For a long time women issues have been causing a lot of misunderstandings. Illegal inequality in social life, sexual violence by their close relatives or at all strangers? WHY???*

Is it just their sex? Women are Mother of future generations. At every step an abuse of them is simple situation. We do not seldom notice it in the streets. Possessions such as they can not take a salary as much as men, can not study in foreign country and they must take a permission to go out somewhere?! If we look at history, the wives of famous people were well-known as their husbands.

For example, Cleopatra-Queen of Egypt, Bibikhanum-the wife of Timur. Those womens were the columns of their Empires. Right, at that time many women were afflicted with hard life-style, but they could fight with their hard times.

Key words: *illegal inequality, social life, Gender Equality, heart power, mother tongue, women's hymn.*

ЖЕНСКАЯ СИЛА

Аннотация. *Женская проблематика уже долгое время вызывает массу недоразумений. Неправомерное неравенство в общественной жизни, сексуальное насилие со стороны близких родственников или вообще чужих людей?*

ПОЧЕМУ???

Это только их пол? Женщины - мать будущих поколений. На каждом шагу насилие над ними - это простая ситуация. Мы не редко замечаем это на улицах. Такие люди, как они, не могут получать такую же зарплату, как я, не могут учиться в чужой стране, и они надо брать разрешение, чтобы куда-то выйти?! Если посмотреть на историю, то жены известных людей были известны как их мужья. Например, Клеопатра-царица Египта, Бибиханум-жена Тимура. Эти женщины были колоннами своих империй. Правда, в то время многие женщины страдали от тяжелого образа жизни, но они могли бороться с трудными временами.

Ключевые слова: *незаконное неравенство, общественная жизнь, гендерное равенство, сила сердца, родной язык, женский гимн.*

Main paragraph

In our modern life problems are many enough to solve. Especially, people even know a woman can do more works and her mental skill is more powerful than men too, while they do not want to admit. If a girl's surroundings become healthy atmosphere, she will achieve more goals than anyone else. According to the facts, girls are more diligent and ambitious than boys.

Therefore, parents and government should create more comfortabilities for them, moreover, in family and social life Gender equality must be imposed completely. While we should not forget which is all laws, equalities begin from our family, that's why atmosphere will be safe when family is good.

Woman has a power, she can grab with it both of family and career life. Women's heart power is similar as grass which is spring grasses may curve when the wind blow, but never give up to grow toward the sun. Like this situation, women do always want to enhance their overall well-being, in spite of all difficulties. As an example I am going to speak about Uzbek poet Zulfiya.

She continued creating her poem after losing her love, husband, father of her young children. Despite all difficulties this woman can bring up her children in the honest, true way. Her poems published a lot of foreign countries, besides Zulfiya Isroilova translated works of many poets, writer from foreign languages to our mother tongue. Especially, her poem named "Bahor keldi seni so'roqlab" is well-known over a lot of countries which is written for her husband's memorize:

Salqin saharlarda, bodom gulida
Binafsha labida, yerlarda bahor.
Qushlarning parvozi, yellarning nozi,
Baxmal vodiylarda, qirlarda bahor...
Qancha sevar eding', bag'rim, bahorni,
O'rik gullarining eding maftuni.
Har uyg'ongan kurtak hayot bergan kabi

Ko'zlaringga surtib o'parding uni. (Zulfiya's poem)

This poem sounds like women's hymn since its written times. Each woman's story is worth to write a poem, who is brave like men, loyal for her family. If more chances are created for women, they can do more things than we think. Zulfiya Isroilova is an example as more powerful person than someone. Like those women over the world are more and more. If who want to live in the bright future, that people, parents should try to educate their generations. So each person ought to look out for their girl, mother, sister and wife's life. They must be defence of their family. That must be main goal of all.

Zulfiya Isroilova (1915-1996)

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